

1. NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS CHARACTERIZATION THROUGH NEURAL NETWORKS, TACKLE THE SMALL TRAINING DATASET

Ava Chavoshi¹, Holger Cebulla¹, Jörg Kaufmann¹
¹Technische Universität Chemnitz, Professur Textile Technologien
Reichenhainerstraße 70
09126 Chemnitz

ABSTRACT

Flax fiber reinforced plastics (FFRPs) present an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic composites due to their low density, high stiffness, and biodegradability. However accurate fiber volume content (FVC) measurement remains challenging with conventional destructive or low-contrast imaging methods. In this work, non-destructive, generative-neural-network-based image segmentation models are developed to improve FVC characterization of FFRPs. High-resolution microscopy images are divided into 256×256-pixel patches and manually annotated into fiber, defect, and matrix classes. U-Net segmentation model is trained with four dataset groups: (1) original data only; (2) geometric augmentation; (3) generative augmentation with a denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) for mask synthesis and a modified SRGAN for mask-to-image translation, and (4) combined geometric and generative augmentations. Performance is evaluated using Intersection over Union (IOU), precision, recall, ROC-AUC, and k-fold test. Geometric augmentation alone led to only a marginal gain, whereas incorporating DDPM/SRGAN synthetic pairs dramatically accelerated convergence and improved IOU values. The full pipeline on the test dataset achieved a peak IOU of 90%, precision and recall above 95%, and class-wise AUCs over 0.98, with reduced performance variance across the test folds. These results demonstrate that generative-based data augmentation enhances segmentation accuracy and reliability for FVC determination in natural fiber composites.

2. INTRODUCTION

Due to their sustainability, strength, stiffness, and low-density, flax fiber (FF) has received attention as an alternative to the common synthetic fibers in field of composite engineering. When compared to common reinforcement fibers, FF shows environmental benefits such as lower energy consumption during production, CO₂ neutrality, and biodegradability [1, 2, 3]. They show favorable mechanical properties, especially when considering their environmental impact [4, 5]. In that regard, flax fiber reinforced plastics (FFRPs) open the opportunity to construct lightweight and durable materials which contribute to environmental conservation without compromising the performance. In determining the true potential of FFRPs, it is essential for them to be precisely characterized; among all, their fiber volume content (FVC). The accurate estimation of FVC is important for prediction of the mechanical properties under load, optimizations, and uniformity of properties in the finished product. As the FF are structurally decomposed in high temperature, an FVC determination using the conventional incineration method is not feasible. In addition, this method is time and energy intensive, and not suitable for rapid quality control processes [6]. X-ray computed tomography can be time and cost intensive for routine quality control processes [7]. The low optical contrast between the FF and the embedding matrix, and the natural irregularities in fiber structure pose a challenge for the conventional image-based FVC characterization methods [3, 8]. Regarding

these challenges, there is need for a non-destructive, accurate, and efficient method for FVC characterization that can cope with the characteristics of FFs. The Neural Network (NN) based image processing methods have been successfully applied to different complex segmentation and feature extraction tasks in field of material characterization [9]. In composite materials characterization, these methods have shown the capabilities to outperform the conventional image processing methods [10, 11, 12]. These models learn directly from data without the need for features to be hand-crafted. Among numerous NN architectures in field of scientific image processing, the U-Net model - originally used for segmentations in biomedical imaging - stands out. This model has a unique U-shaped structure made of two encoder-decoder paths. One contracting path (encoder) for capturing features and one expanding path (decoder) for precise localization of those features. One special benefit of this model is its ability to result in high accurate segmentation when working with small low resolution datasets [13]. Transfer learning leads to faster and more stable convergence in the training process and enhances feature extraction capabilities in terms of precision and recall specially when it comes to low contrast and noisy images [14, 15, 16, 17]. The unique structure of NN models make them starve for vast data to reach high accuracies in the training phase. This can pose a problem when calculating the FVC with the small datasets of microcopy images from FFRPs. Although the conventional geometric based data augmentation method can alleviate this problem to some extent, it cannot produce a wide enough range of diversity to cover the possible unseen features in the test datasets. The generative models can mitigate the augmentation limitation by learning from available real data and generating synthetic but realistic data.

In field of image generation, currently the Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [18] are the state of the art [19]. GANs work based on an adversarial scenario where the generator and discriminator compete with each other. The generator tries to produce synthetic data which are not distinguishable from real by the discriminator, and the discriminator tries to keep from being fooled. Ledig et al. [20], introduced SRGAN as an approach to image super-resolution. Instead of optimizing a simple pixel-wise mean squared error (MSE), a deep residual network with skip connections and a perceptual loss computed on high-level VGG feature maps were used. This enables the network to capture fine texture details and consequently to generate realistic high-resolution images from the low-resolution pairs. This SRGAN structure was later modified for the purpose of medical image resolution enhancement [21]. Main modifications were (a) A multi-scale shallow feature extraction module through parallel convolutional branches with kernel sizes of 3, 5, and 7 that improves capturing of features at various scales and is important for preserving subtle image structures. (b) Enhancing the discriminator by using additional convolutional layers with skip connections which helps to improve the adversarial training and to reduce problems like vanishing gradients. (c) An extra loss component (L1) - in addition to the adversarial and VGG-based perceptual losses - which penalizes large reconstruction errors and leads to smoother and more realistic images. In this work, this modified SRGAN is adapted to the task of mask-to-image translation.

In addition to GANs, research has shown the ability of the likelihood-based models as another state of the art in generating high diversity synthetic data [22]. Among the likelihood-based models, Diffusion models specifically show easier and more stable training and high-quality generated images [23]. The images by these models are generated through removing noise from a signal [24]. In terms of producing realistic images, both model types (GAN and DDPM) have significant advancements; however, DDPM is superior in terms of stability and controllability, while GAN excels in terms of realism [25]. In this work the DDPM model was chosen to generate the realistic synthetic masks and the GAN model to translate these to

realistic accordingly images. The goal of this work is to study the effect of generative-based data augmentation on segmentation task in FVC determination of FFRPs. To this goal, a step-by-step experiment is followed, each step containing a specific augmentation pipeline, with the most sophisticated step being the combination of GAN and DDPM models to generate new realistic synthetic data for training of the U-Net segmentation model. The DDPM model is trained on real masks and learns to generate realistic looking new synthetic masks. The GAN model is trained on the real data and learns the translation from masks to images. This trained model is later used to translate the synthetic masks generated by DDPM model into accordingly realistic looking synthetic images. The robustness of the developed model in feature extraction is demonstrated and its capabilities in generalization to new unseen data is tested. The training with the generated data showed a stable training and validation process, and higher accuracy on inference data. The combination of the generative data and the geometrical augmentation showed the best results.

3. RESEARCH TESTS & EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Sample preparation and data acquisition

Unidirectional textile preforms of FF roving were made by automated fiber placement process. After vacuum infusion using epoxy resin and then curing, small specimens of size 10×10 mm were cut out using water jet. For the purpose of preparation for microscopy imaging, these specimens are embedded into ambient temperature curing epoxy resin and kept until the curing is done. These embedded samples were then sanded and polished to the maximum surface smoothness. This smoothness guarantees a clear image focus all over the imaging surface. Microcopy was done using Keyence VHX-600 3D digital microscope with a magnification of 100X and images were transferred to a host computer for the further processing.

3.2 Data preparation

The high resolution of the microscopy images requires enormous memory for the training processes. To mitigate this challenge, smaller patches of size 256×256-pixel were extracted from the original images to be used for model training purposes. This size for the patches is not too big to cause memory exhaustion but big enough to reasonably represent the features in the original images. In order to avoid possible overfitting problems during training, they were extracted without any overlaps and from different images. In order to challenge the generalization abilities of the models, on purpose only 27 patches were extracted and used. Each patch was carefully manually annotated to three classes of fiber, defect, and matrix. These annotated patches are used as the ground truth masks for the training and testing of the models.

3.3 Model Training

Four training steps were designed and implemented, which will be described in the following. **Step 1.** Training with the original image patches (20 training and 7 validation images) to serve as a baseline for the following training steps. U-net is used as the model architecture. For the purpose of transfer learning, weights of the VGG19 model pretrained on 2012 ILSVRC ImageNet dataset were used [26, 27]. As for metrics, Intersection over Union (IOU), and for loss a combination of Binary Focal Loss and Categorical Focal Loss was used, along with Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and SoftMax activation function. Trainings are run for 50 epochs on GPU GeForce RTX 4090 with 24 gigabytes of VRAM. Fig. 1 shows the IOU throughout the training and validation.

Figure 1. IOU during training (left) and validation (right) of the 4 training steps

Step 2. Increasing the versatility of training data and so the performance of training by using geometrical transformation-based data augmentation [28]. Using the Albumentations library [29], an augmentation pipeline consisting of a set of image transformations (i.e. rotate, flip, hue-brightness-contrast shuffle, blur, noise, and grid distortion) with varying probabilities was established. Image-mask pairs went through this pipeline and received the exact same transformations and were stored in a new path. Both training and validation data went through this pipeline, and it led to a total number of 200 training and 70 validation images. Training of the segmentation U-net was carried out with the same parameters as in step 1, results are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Step 3. Data augmentation using generative models. In this step a unique combination of two generative models is used. A diffusion-based model to generate synthetic masks, and a GAN-based model for translation of these generated masks to corresponding realistic looking synthetic images. The Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) [24] is Unet-based, tailored for diffusion models with six convolutional blocks with progressively increasing feature channels (128, 128, 256, 256, 512, 512) including both standard down/up-sampling blocks and attention-based modules. The noise scheduler is set up with 1000 timesteps. The model is trained for 400 epochs with batch size 8, using the AdamW optimizer for better generalization and a cosine learning rate scheduler with warm-up to stabilize training at early stages. The learning rate is set to 0.0001. For each training iteration, random noise was added to the input images according to the predefined noise schedule, and the model was optimized to predict the noise component using a mean squared error loss. To ensure reproducibility, all random seeds were fixed, and mixed precision training (fp16) was employed. The Frechet Inception Distance (FID) is used as assessment metric, calculated by comparing a set of generated images against a subset of real images. The training metrics are illustrated in Fig. 2. After training, 200 synthetic masks were generated. The resemblance between real and generated masks is compared in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. DDPM model Training metrics show constant decrease in average loss and a general decrease in FID

Figure 3. Visual resemblance between real and generated masks by DDPM – not to be compared in pairs

Subsequently, the structure of the modified-SRGAN introduced by Ahmad et. al. [21] is adapted to the mask-to-image translation task. It is done by changing the structure of the generator into a U-Net encoder-decoder framework which incorporates the multi-scale feature extraction from the modified SRGAN. The encoder extracts deep features and the decoder with the skip connections preserves the spatial details during reconstruction. For adapting to the segmentation task, the discriminator is constructed in form of a PatchGAN to evaluate the generated images on a local scale. Moreover, in addition to the adversarial loss and MSE loss, an L1 loss is employed. The goal of combining the losses is to improve the model’s ability to maintain structural details and smooth transitions and to generate images indistinguishable from real images. The model was trained for 200 epochs, and training metrics are shown in Fig. 5. After training, the model was used to translate the 200 generated masks from DDPM into corresponding synthetic images (Fig. 4). These synthetic image-mask pairs are divided to training and validation sets (150:50) and are combined with the real image-mask pairs from step two which leads to a dataset of 350 train and 120 validation data. Data were shuffled to make sure real and synthetic data are distributed randomly. Training of the segmentation U-net was carried out with the same parameters as in step 1 and results are shown in Fig. 1. The whole process of step 3 is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 4. Visual comparison of GAN-based mask2image translation reveals high resemblance between synthetic and real images

Figure 5. GAN-based model training metrics show constant decrease in generator loss and FID

Step 4. Effect of geometrical transformation-based data augmentation on training with the real/synthetic data set. The training dataset from step 3 (350 train and 120 validation) is further geometrically augmented to 640 training and 220 validation data. This step is carried out in order to study how the combination of conventional and generative-based data augmentation would affect the performance of the segmentation model. Training of the segmentation U-net was carried out with the same parameters as in step 1 and results are illustrated in Fig. 1.

3.4 Inference Evaluation

In order to evaluate the inference capabilities of models in steps 1 to 4, all models were tested on a constant dataset of unseen image patches. IOU score, precision, and recall were calculated and illustrated in Fig. 7.

Figure 6. DDPM and SRGAN combined to generate pairs of synthetic images/masks

Figure 7. IOU, precision, and recall of steps 1-4 models on test data

To test the robustness and generalization abilities of models on possible uneven feature distributions, the test dataset is divided into 5 equal folds and fed to the model for purpose of inference, and precision and recall are recorded. This is done for each trained model in steps 1-4. The results are shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Precision and recall result of 5-fold test (top), average and standard deviation of all folds for each training step (bottom)

In addition to precision and recall and in order to have an outlook on how the segmentation models can distinguish between classes; the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Confusion Matrix are derived. The results are in Fig. 9 and 10, respectively.

Figure 9. Multi-class ROC on test data, true positive rates increase for all three classes from step 1 to 4

Figure 10. Confusion Matrix on test data, correct predictions increase for all three classes from step 1 to 4

4. RESULTS

4.1 Segmentation performance across augmentation steps

The geometrical transformation-based augmentation pipeline in step two didn't lead to a remarkable change in training process, as the IOU only increased to 89% - compared to the training IOU of 88% from step one (Fig. 1). In the validation however, step two shows a more stable increase in IOU score in which the final value reached 88% compared to 83% of step one. The DDPM-GAN-based augmentation pipeline in step 3 boosted the training convergence, in such a way that the training started with an IOU score of 82% - compared to 28% of step one. The IOU at the end of training is 92% - compared to 83% of step one. This consequently led to higher stability and increase in IOU during Validation (Fig. 1). Application of both generative and geometric transforms in step 4, shows the best results among all. The training and validation are fast converging and highly stable, with the final IOU of 95% and 92%,

respectively. (Fig. 1). Performance metrics of inferences on unseen data show the similar trends as training and validations processes. Compared to step 1, IOU, precision, and recall reached 90%, 95%, and 95%, which compared to step 1 show an improvement of 59%, 30%, and 33%, respectively (Fig. 7).

4.2 Performance of augmentation generative models

As shown in Fig. 2, the DDPM model's average loss showed a sharp drop during the first 10 epochs and continued decreasing steadily over the rest of the training (Fig. 2-left). The FID value showed fluctuations during the training; however, the general trend shows a decrease from 5.5 to 1.24 (Fig. 2-right). The visual inspection of the generated masks (Fig. 3) reveals the ability of the model to capture the irregular, low-contrast fiber geometries seen in real data, which provide samples beyond what simple geometric transformations could produce. In terms of generator loss, the mask-to-Image translation using the modified SRGAN model showed a sharp drop in the beginning of training and kept lowering smoothly over the 200 epochs (Fig. 5). Same trend was to see with the FID score, decreasing from 5.7 to 0.2. Translated images show realistic fiber-matrix boundaries, and fiber and defect textures (Fig. 4). This confirms that the combined DDPM/SRGAN pipeline (Fig. 6) can effectively bridge the mask and image domains which yields to high-fidelity synthetic pairs, to be used for the segmentation U-Net model training.

4.3 Class-wise discrimination

Multi-class ROC curves (Fig. 9) are tools to illustrate the ability of the segmentation model to distinguish between the classes in the images. Here, an incremental increase in AUC for fiber, matrix, and defect classes from Step 1 to 4 is obvious. In step 4 the AUC for fiber, matrix, and defect classes has reached 0.98, 0.99, and 0.99, which compared to step 1, shows an increase of 27%, 41%, and 29%, respectively. The confusion matrix (Fig. 10) shows how the model is performing to identify the classes correctly or not. For an easier comparison, the correct predictions are illustrated in Fig. 11. The struggle of the model in step 1 in correctly distinguishing the fiber (67% correct predictions) is obvious, while in step 4 this has increased to 95% which equals to an improvement of 42%. This improvement for the defect and matrix classes is 7% and 39%, respectively. These indicate that model's sensitivity has drastically improved in distinguishing between the classes without being fooled even when there is low visual contrast in images between the different classes.

Figure 11. Correct predictions for each class through step 1 to 4

4.4 Robustness and generalization

As different images in the data set have different feature distribution, the unseen test data set was partitioned into 5 folds. After each step of augmentation, an inference was carried out using the trained model on these five folds. Fig. 8 shows how the precision and recall are increasing in each step. Fig. 9 illustrates the average and standard deviation of precision and recall of folds in each step. In this figure, the effect of each augmentation step is clearly visible. Step 4 not only has the highest precision (91% compared to 58% of step 1) and recall (92% compared to 43% of step 1) but also shows the smallest variation between the folds. Another point to notice here is that the average precision and recall are reaching a balance through the augmentation steps. These indicate that the combined generative and transformative augmentation notably stabilizes performance even when feature distributions vary.

4.5 Visual comparison

Finally, a visual comparison can give a better insight into the segmentation capabilities of the models through the four augmentation steps. Fig.12 illustrates two sample images of the test data set. In the middle, the segmentation results of each of these images through the augmentations steps 1-4 are shown. Steps 1 and 2 do not return acceptable segmentation results for neither of the two test images. For the first image almost all the fiber class has been overlooked and for the second image, except a small part of the fiber class, everything else has been detected as defect class, almost completely overlooking the background class. Step 3 had a leap improvement in detecting the fiber class in the first image but still struggling in some areas. While for the second image the model is now better able to detect the background class, this is still no meaningful segmentation. Looking at the results from step 4 reveals a clear improvement. For both test images the classes have been effectively detected and discriminated from each other, in accordance with the high correct predictions demonstrated by the confusion matrix earlier.

Figure 12. Predicted masks in each augmentation step

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study a novel, non-destructive methodology for FVC estimation of flax fiber composites was established. This was done by using advanced generative augmentation within a U-Net segmentation framework. The combination of DDPM for synthesis of realistic masks and modified SRGAN for mask-to-image translation significantly improved the diversity of the training dataset. This accordingly resulted in faster convergence and more stable training

performance compared to purely geometric transformations. The combined generative and geometric augmentation approach achieved the highest metrics - 90 % IoU, 95 % precision, 95 % recall, and ROC-AUC values over 0.98 for all segmentation classes - while simultaneously reduced the sensitivity to variability of feature distribution in the unseen test dataset, as a sign of enhanced generalization abilities of the model. The results suggest that the combination of generative and transformative-based data augmentation is able to overcome the challenge of limited and low-contrast microscopy datasets in FVC characterizations in composite materials. It is to be noted that this study relied on a small laboratory-scale dataset of only flax fibers in thermoset epoxy matrix, captured under controlled lighting conditions. Therefore, to validate the results, future work can focus on creating a larger more diverse image data set from different natural fiber/matrix material combinations under varying imaging conditions.

Acknowledgment: This work has been funded by the Europäischen Sozialfonds Plus (ESF Plus) through the Sächsische Aufbaubank – Förderbank (SAB) for the junior research group “autoPre” (Antragsnummer: 100693526)

6. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Fleischmann et al., “Funktionalisierung von Low-Twist Flachsgarnen für bauteilformnahes Preforming,” presented at the Chemnitzer Textiltechnik-Tagung, Chemnitz, 29.09 2022, p. S. 81-89.
- [2] E. Sparnins, “Mechanical Properties of Flax Fibers and Their Composites,” Division of Polymer Engineering, Department of Applied Physics and Mechanical Engineering, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden, 2009.
- [3] L. Yan, N. Chouw, and K. Jayaraman, “Flax fibre and its composites – A review,” *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 56, pp. 296–317, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2013.08.014.
- [4] O. Faruk, A. K. Bledzki, H.-P. Fink, and M. Sain, “Biocomposites reinforced with natural fibers: 2000–2010,” *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1552–1596, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2012.04.003.
- [5] K. L. Pickering, M. G. A. Efendy, and T. M. Le, “A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance,” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 83, pp. 98–112, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.08.038.
- [6] N. K. Kim, S. Dutta, and D. Bhattacharyya, “A review of flammability of natural fibre reinforced polymeric composites,” *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 162, pp. 64–78, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.04.016.
- [7] I. Hanhan, R. Agyei, X. Xiao, and M. D. Sangid, “Comparing non-destructive 3D X-ray computed tomography with destructive optical microscopy for microstructural characterization of fiber reinforced composites,” *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 184, p. 107843, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2019.107843.
- [8] J. Summerscales, N. Dissanayake, A. Virk, and W. Hall, “A review of bast fibres and their composites. Part 2 – Composites,” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 1336–1344, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.05.020.
- [9] Z. Yang et al., “Deep learning approaches for mining structure-property linkages in high contrast composites from simulation datasets,” *Computational Materials Science*, vol. 151, pp. 278–287, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.commatsci.2018.05.014.
- [10] A. C. Huang, S. H. Meng, and T. J. Huang, “A survey on machine and deep learning in semiconductor industry: methods, opportunities, and challenges,” *Cluster Comput*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 3437–3472, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10586-023-04115-6.
- [11] M. Saqlain, Q. Abbas, and J. Y. Lee, “A Deep Convolutional Neural Network for Wafer Defect Identification on an Imbalanced Dataset in Semiconductor Manufacturing Processes,” *IEEE*

- Trans. Semicond. Manufact.*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 436–444, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TSM.2020.2994357.
- [12] S. Das, S. S. A. M, and S. Jayaram, “Deep Learning Convolutional Neural Network for Defect Identification and Classification in Woven Fabric,” *IJAINN*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 9–13, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.35940/ijainn.B1011.041221.
- [13] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, “U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation,” 2015, doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.1505.04597.
- [14] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, “Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition,” 2014, doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.1409.1556.
- [15] “Segmentation Models: Python library with Neural Networks for Image Segmentation based on Keras and TensorFlow.” Accessed: Feb. 05, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/qubvel/segmentation_models
- [16] Upper Austrian University of Applied Sciences (FH OÖ) *et al.*, “Usage of 3D U-net Convolutional Neural Network for the inspection of aerospace components,” *eJNDT*, vol. 28, no. 3, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.58286/27728.
- [17] J. Wu *et al.*, “A state-of-the-art survey of U-Net in microscopic image analysis: from simple usage to structure mortification,” *Neural Comput & Applic*, vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 3317–3346, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00521-023-09284-4.
- [18] I. J. Goodfellow *et al.*, “Generative Adversarial Networks,” Jun. 10, 2014, *arXiv*: arXiv:1406.2661. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1406.2661.
- [19] T. Karras, S. Laine, M. Aittala, J. Hellsten, J. Lehtinen, and T. Aila, “Analyzing and Improving the Image Quality of StyleGAN,” Mar. 23, 2020, *arXiv*: arXiv:1912.04958. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1912.04958.
- [20] C. Ledig *et al.*, “Photo-Realistic Single Image Super-Resolution Using a Generative Adversarial Network,” May 25, 2017, *arXiv*: arXiv:1609.04802. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1609.04802.
- [21] Waqar Ahmad, Hazrat Ali, and Shoaib Azmat, “A new generative adversarial network for medical images super resolution,” *Sci Rep*, vol. 12, p. 9533, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-13658-4>.
- [22] A. Razavi, A. van den Oord, and O. Vinyals, “Generating Diverse High-Fidelity Images with VQ-VAE-2,” Jun. 02, 2019, *arXiv*: arXiv:1906.00446. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1906.00446.
- [23] J. Sohl-Dickstein, E. A. Weiss, N. Maheswaranathan, and S. Ganguli, “Deep Unsupervised Learning using Nonequilibrium Thermodynamics,” Nov. 18, 2015, *arXiv*: arXiv:1503.03585. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1503.03585.
- [24] J. Ho, A. Jain, and P. Abbeel, “Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models,” Dec. 16, 2020, *arXiv*: arXiv:2006.11239. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2006.11239.
- [25] Yingying Peng, “A Comparative Analysis Between GAN and Diffusion Models in Image Generation,” presented at the 2nd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Database and Machine Learning (AIDML 2024), Rotterdam, Netherlands, Jul. 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://www.aidml.org>
- [26] Y. Zheng, C. Yang, and A. Merkulov, “Breast cancer screening using convolutional neural network and follow-up digital mammography,” in *Computational Imaging III*, A. Ashok, J. C. Petrucci, A. Mahalanobis, and L. Tian, Eds., Orlando, United States: SPIE, May 2018, p. 4. doi: 10.1117/12.2304564.
- [27] P. Iakubovskii, “Segmentation Models.” Accessed: Aug. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/qubvel/segmentation_models
- [28] F. López De La Rosa, J. L. Gómez-Sirvent, R. Sánchez-Reolid, R. Morales, and A. Fernández-Caballero, “Geometric transformation-based data augmentation on defect classification of segmented images of semiconductor materials using a ResNet50 convolutional neural network,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 206, p. 117731, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2022.117731.
- [29] “Albumentations image augmentation library.” Accessed: Feb. 05, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://albumentations.ai/docs/>